

A Low-Complexity Method for Processing EIS Data of R-RC Circuit and Parameter Identification

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Abstract—This paper presents a method for analyzing impedance of various electrochemical sources, or electrode-electrolyte interface, with the aim of estimating the values of the equivalent R-RC circuit parameters. The proposed method utilizes characteristic frequency, resistance at the characteristic frequency, and reactance at the characteristic frequency for parameter estimation. It eliminates the need for specialized software, initial values, and computationally intensive processes. Initial verification, performed using the synthetic impedance datasets, showed that the proposed method can provide reliable estimations. Moreover, positive results in terms of reducing the impact of noise levels on the accuracy of model parameters estimation are obtained using the exponential filter.

Keywords—Equivalent R-RC circuit, exponential filter, characteristic frequency, impedance analysis, parameter estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is a characterization method that consists of applying alternating voltage/current of known amplitude and phase angle, and measuring of the response (current/voltage, respectively). By finding the corresponding values of amplitude and phase angle of the response, it is possible to obtain complex impedance (modulus and argument) of the analyzed object. Electrical impedance can be an indicator of general properties of the material, but it also can be an indicator of the very specific conditions. Reported applications of EIS data include studying fuel cells [1], diagnostics on lithium-ion batteries [2], [3], lead-acid batteries [4], porosity estimation [5], *etc.*

Collecting impedance data is the first part of EIS. Obtained data can be processed by direct comparison of impedance modulus and/or argument in the various conditions. Such an approach requires very strict regulation of the environmental conditions and other parameters, which will ensure that impedance changes are only due to the variations in parameter of interest. In many practical applications, it is not possible to control all parameters that can have influence on impedance, and because of that approach in which equivalent electrical circuits are used to fit obtained impedance is very popular [6]. The main idea is to create an equivalent electrical circuit which will mimic the measured impedance in the given frequency range. Circuit elements are related with the specific processes and structure elements of the object, which enables establishment of correlation and reliable recognition of causes of impedance changes. During past times, a certain number of equivalent electrical circuits became very popular and commonly used in some fields. One example is circuit composed of two resistors and one capacitor, also known as R-RC, 2R-1C or simplified Randles circuit [7], with frequent application in analysis of the electrochemical sources and

interfaces, such as lithium ion batteries [8], [9], supercapacitors [10], photovoltaic elements [11], *etc.*

The focus of this work is to present a method for parameter identification of the R-RC circuit, based on the estimated values of characteristic frequency, as well as resistance and reactance at the characteristic frequency. Such a method advances state of the art because it does not need PC-based software, and it does not require initial values provided by the user.

II. THE PROPOSED METHOD

R-RC circuit is composed of resistor R_s in series with parallel combination of resistor R_p and capacitor C_p . The complex impedance of R-RC circuit is composed of real $R(\omega)$ and imaginary part $X(\omega)$, which are functions of angular frequency ω (rad/s), and model parameters (R_s , R_p and C_p):

$$R(\omega) = \frac{R_s + R_p + \omega^2 R_s R_p^2 C_p^2}{1 + \omega^2 R_p^2 C_p^2} \quad (1)$$

$$X(\omega) = \frac{-\omega C_p R_p^2}{1 + \omega^2 R_p^2 C_p^2} \quad (2)$$

By finding the first derivative of $X(\omega)$ with respect to ω and by equalizing it to zero, it is possible to get an angular frequency at which X has the minimum value. This angular frequency, also known and as characteristic angular frequency (ω_0) has analytical solution dependent on the values of model parameters:

$$\omega_0 = \frac{1}{R_p C_p} \quad (3)$$

By putting (3) to (1) and (2), the corresponding values of real and imaginary part at such frequency can be determined (R_0 and X_0), enabling the finding of analytical solution with respect to model parameters (R_s , R_p and C_p):

$$R_s = R_0 + X_0 \quad (4)$$

$$R_p = -2 \cdot X_0 \quad (5)$$

$$C_p = -\frac{1}{2 \cdot \omega_0 \cdot X_0} \quad (6)$$

III. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Noiseless synthetic dataset

We used (1) and (2) to create simulated real and imaginary part of impedance with the given nominal values of model parameters ($R_s=220 \Omega$, $R_p=1 \text{ k}\Omega$ and $C_p=3.3 \text{ nF}$). These values were randomly selected from the set of nominal values that are commercially available as discrete

components. The number of measurement points was $N=100$, with linear frequency range from 1 kHz to 100 kHz. Estimated values were: $R_s=222.38 \Omega$, $R_p=999.99 \Omega$ and $C_p=3.32 \text{ nF}$. Relative errors in estimation of model parameters R_s , R_p and C_p are 1.08%, 0.005% and 0.48%, respectively. The actual characteristic frequency is 48228.77 Hz, while the estimated value is 48 kHz. Therefore, in estimating characteristic frequency, the relative error is 0.47%. Fig. 1 (a) displays a Nyquist plot of reference and estimated values, while Fig. 1 (b) shows the residual curves of the fitting to the reference values of real and imaginary part of impedance.

Fig. 1. (a) Nyquist plots of reference and estimated values in case of noiseless data, (b) the residual curve of the fitting to the reference values of impedance.

B. Synthetic dataset with 0.25% random noise

With the aim to create a more realistic impedance dataset, a 0.25% random noise was added to the impedance values calculated using (1) and (2). The number of measurement points was again $N=100$, and linear frequency range from 1 kHz to 100 kHz. Estimated values in this case were: $R_s=212.35 \Omega$, $R_p=1000.92 \Omega$ and $C_p=3.25 \text{ nF}$. Relative errors in estimation of model parameters R_s , R_p and C_p are 3.48%, 0.09% and 1.66%, respectively. The actual characteristic frequency is 48228.77 Hz, while the estimated value is 49 kHz. Therefore, the presence of the noise increased the relative error in characteristic frequency estimation to 1.60%. Fig. 2 (a) displays a Nyquist plot of reference and estimated values, while Fig. 2 (b) shows the residual curves of the fitting to the reference values of real and imaginary part of impedance.

Fig. 2. (a) Nyquist plots of reference and estimated values in case of data with 0.25% random noise, (b) the residual curve of the fitting to the reference values of impedance.

C. Filtering with the exponential filter

Increased errors in parameter estimation using dataset with included noise emphasized need for a proper signal filtering. Filters can be deployed in the measurement chain, but a very convenient way, in the case of microcontroller-based signal processing, is the use of digital filters. One example is exponential filter. Exponential filter belongs to the group of recursive filters. That means that a filtered value (y_i) is calculated using the previous filtered value (y_{i-1}) and new measurement (x_i):

$$y_i = w \cdot y_{i-1} + (1 - w) \cdot x_i \quad (7)$$

where w is in the range (0,1), and it is the weighting factor that controls the level of smoothing. Filtering was implemented for both resistance and reactance. Input data to the filter was composed of resistance and reactance from noisy dataset (noise level was varied from 0.25%, to 0.5%, 1%, 2%, 5% and 10%). We implemented this filter in such a way that w was varied from 0 to 1 with the linear step of 0.01, while the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between filtered and noiseless data is monitored. The criterium for selecting optimal value of w is the smallest sum of MSE for resistance and reactance. A summary of estimated values for raw (noisy) and filtered data is given in Table I. As it can be seen from Table I, increase of noise level leads to higher deviations of the estimated values when compared to the reference values. However, the used filter was shown to be capable of reducing the noise impact

even in cases of high noise levels, such as 10%. It is also interesting to notice that exponential filter had better efficiency in terms of reduced relative errors in estimated values of model parameters with higher noise levels.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF ESTIMATION RESULTS USING RAW AND FILTERED DATA FOR VARIOUS NOISE LEVELS.

Noise level	Raw/filtered	R_s (Ω)	R_p (Ω)	C_p (nF)
Reference	Not applicable	220.00	1000.00	3.30
0%	Not applicable	222.38	999.99	3.32
0.25%	Raw	212.35	1000.92	3.25
	Filtered ($w=1.00$)	212.35	1000.92	3.25
0.5%	Raw	212.58	1001.97	3.24
	Filtered ($w=0.99$)	212.68	1001.96	3.24
1%	Raw	203.33	1004.44	3.17
	Filtered ($w=0.97$)	203.63	1004.43	3.17
2%	Raw	204.36	1009.53	3.15
	Filtered ($w=0.87$)	205.79	1009.30	3.15
5%	Raw	150.75	1031.54	2.71
	Filtered ($w=0.68$)	211.68	1022.21	3.11
10%	Raw	157.37	1076.88	2.59
	Filtered ($w=0.51$)	220.16	1038.37	3.07

For the better illustration of how filtering reduced relative errors in estimation of model parameter, comparison of relative errors is given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Comparison of relative errors for estimated values of model parameters when raw and filtered data was used.

Table I also shows the values of weighting factor w . It is important to emphasize that those values were selected based on the MSE values, without subjective input from the user. The supporting plots of total MSE (sum of MSE for real and imaginary part) as the function of the weighting factor w are given in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The total MSE as the function of the weighting factor w .

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The main scope of this work was to create an analytical solution with three equations in closed form, from which it will be possible to estimate values of R-RC model parameters (R_s , R_p and C_p). The advantage of the proposed method lies in the fact that values of characteristic frequency, resistance and reactance are only needed for estimation.

Initial verification performed using the synthetic impedance datasets showed that the proposed method can provide reliable estimation results. However, the impact of measurement noise on estimation accuracy is also recognized. Therefore, a proper filtering of the input values is required in cases of extensive noise levels. Positive results in terms of reducing relative errors in estimation of model parameters are obtained using the exponential filter.

Our future work will be directed towards further analysis and validation of the proposed system. We will perform analysis with varying number of measurement points, types of frequency distribution (linear and logarithmic). Moreover, use of experimentally obtained impedance and comparison with the related work from the literature should be performed. The suitability of the proposed method for implementation on the low-cost hardware, such as microcontroller-based board, will also be explored.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Padha, S. Verma, P. Mahajan, and S. Arya, "Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) Performance Analysis and Challenges in Fuel Cell Applications," *J. Electrochem. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 167–176, May 2022, doi: 10.33961/jecst.2021.01263.
- [2] M. Crescentini *et al.*, "Online EIS and diagnostics on lithium-ion batteries by means of low-power integrated sensing and parametric modeling," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 70, pp. 1–11, 2020.
- [3] I. Babaeiyazdi, A. Rezaei-Zare, and S. Shokrzadeh, "State of charge prediction of EV Li-ion batteries using EIS: A machine learning

- approach,” *Energy*, vol. 223, p. 120116, May 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2021.120116.
- [4] T. Murariu and C. Morari, “Time-dependent analysis of the state-of-health for lead-acid batteries: An EIS study,” *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 21, pp. 87–93, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2018.11.011.
- [5] H. Fakhri Nabavi and M. Aliofkhaeaei, “Morphology, composition and electrochemical properties of bioactive-TiO₂/HA on CP-Ti and Ti6Al4V substrates fabricated by alkali treatment of hybrid plasma electrolytic oxidation process (estimation of porosity from EIS results),” *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 375, pp. 266–291, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.surfcoat.2019.07.032.
- [6] X. Lai, S. Wang, S. Ma, J. Xie, and Y. Zheng, “Parameter sensitivity analysis and simplification of equivalent circuit model for the state of charge of lithium-ion batteries,” *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 330, p. 135239, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.electacta.2019.135239.
- [7] J. E. B. Randles, “Kinetics of rapid electrode reactions,” *Discussions of the faraday society*, vol. 1, pp. 11–19, 1947.
- [8] U. Tröltzsch, O. Kanoun, and H.-R. Tränkler, “Characterizing aging effects of lithium ion batteries by impedance spectroscopy,” *Electrochimica acta*, vol. 51, no. 8–9, pp. 1664–1672, 2006.
- [9] N. Meddings *et al.*, “Application of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy to commercial Li-ion cells: A review,” *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 480, p. 228742, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.228742.
- [10] H. Rahimi-Eichi, F. Baronti, and M.-Y. Chow, “Online adaptive parameter identification and state-of-charge coestimation for lithium-polymer battery cells,” *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 2053–2061, 2013.
- [11] E. von Hauff, “Impedance Spectroscopy for Emerging Photovoltaics,” *J. Phys. Chem. C*, vol. 123, no. 18, pp. 11329–11346, May 2019, doi: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b00892.